

Research Article

Connect2Cap 2.0

Mohd Syazwan Zainal^{1,*}, Salmiah Bujang², Siti Nurul Atikah Mohd Arifin³, Noor Fajariah Nordin³, Suhaila Suhaimi³, Syahiran Razali³, and Puteri Ainnatasya Yahkup³

¹ Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; syazwanzainal@ukm.edu.my; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1450-2760>

² Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; salmiahbujang@ukm.edu.my; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-6247-6589>

³ Makmal Pembelajaran Autisme, Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; malautisme@ukm.edu.my

* Correspondence: syazwanzainal@ukm.edu.my; 017-6652610

Abstract: *Students with Special Educational Needs (SEN), especially those with autism, often struggle with fine motor skills, such as finger muscle strength, hand coordination, and movement control. They also face challenges in visual discrimination and color matching. These issues not only affect their readiness for pre-writing activities but also limit their engagement in the learning process. To tackle these problems, Connect2Cap 2.0 was created as an autism-friendly teaching aid. It aims to improve finger strength and support cognitive development through structured, color-matching activities. This version is more challenging and engaging than the previous Connect2Cap 1.0 model version. The effectiveness of this tool was tested through systematic observation of two male SEN students with autism, aged four and five, during a six-week intervention. A pre-post observation checklist measured their ability to match colors on caps by stretching rubber bands across three color categories: red, yellow, and blue. Teacher was also interviewed to provide feedback on the usability of Connect2Cap 2.0. The results showed a consistent improvement in both students' color-matching abilities. The teacher feedback indicated that the product was practical and effective for teaching purposes. Overall, Connect2Cap 2.0 not only strengthens finger muscles and focus among SEN students but also has the potential to work in mainstream preschool environments with necessary adjustments based on students' abilities and teachers' creativity. The product is now in the process of intellectual property registration at Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM), highlighting its role in promoting inclusive and engaging learning for SEN students.*

Keywords: teaching aids; student with special needs; autism

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Children with Special Education Needs (SEN), especially those who have been identified as having autism spectrum disorder (ASD), generally face significant handicaps in fine motor control and expression tasks, such as finger muscle strength, hand coordination, and movement control. These constraints are strongly related to issues of visual discrimination and color matching, which are fundamental for early literacy and other learning skills (Gonzalez et al., 2024). Deficient fine motor skills in children with autism have been linked to more extensive cognitive and communicative difficulties, inhibiting the development of pre-writing skills that are crucial for future academic mastery (Lin et al., 2024).

To address these challenges, this study introduces Connect2Cap 2.0, an autism-friendly educational tool designed to strengthen finger muscles and support cognitive growth through structured color-matching activities. Building upon the earlier Connect2Cap 1.0 model, this version integrates gamified and art-based learning strategies to enhance engagement, coordination, and attention among young autistic learners (Huili et al., 2023). The tool’s design is grounded in pedagogical principles emphasizing repetition, immediate feedback, and gradual task progression approaches proven effective in therapeutic and educational interventions for children with ASD (Fasikhah & Yustika, 2025; Mohandass et al., 2023).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

To evaluate the effectiveness of Connect2Cap 2.0, a six-week observation-based intervention was conducted with two students diagnosed with ASD, both aged four and five years old. Throughout the intervention, performance was assessed using a pre- and post-checklist that measured color matching accuracy and hand coordination while stretching rubber bands across different colored caps (red, yellow, and blue). Teacher interviews further documented the perceived usability of Connect2Cap 2.0 in teaching and learning activities.

2.1 Participants

This study involved two students diagnosed with ASD: the participants, aged 4 and 5 years, demonstrated similar characteristics in their learning needs, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Participants Information: Students

Participants	Gender	Aged	Characteristics
A	Boy	4 years old	Low-functioning autism is often associated with limitations in fine motor skills, thus requiring appropriate learning materials to strengthen finger muscles and enhance focus on learning.
B	Boy	5 years old	

Table 2 shows the teacher information who also involve as participant in this study.

Table 2. Participant Information: Teacher

Teacher	Gender	Aged	Experience
Noor	Female	39 years	10 years

2.2 Material

Figure 1. This is a figure of Connect2Cap 2.0

2.3 Instruments

Data were collected using two instruments: a pre–post observation checklist for monitoring participants’ mastery of Connect2Cap 2.0 activities and a semi-structured usability interview protocol.

2.4 Data Collection and Analysis

Table 3 presents a comprehensive outline of the data collection and analysis procedures implemented in this study.

Table 3. Data Collection and Analysis

Type of Data	Data Collection Procedure	Data Analysis Procedure
Pre-Post Data	Observation	Descriptive analysis
Usability	Interview	Thematic analysis

3. FINDINGS

The findings related to the implementation of Connect2Cap 2.0 were organized into two primary domains to strengthen the depth and credibility of the analysis. The first domain concerns the impact on activity mastery among the two participants, providing direct evidence of the intervention’s effectiveness in enhancing their fine motor and cognitive skills. The second domain involves teachers’ evaluative feedback on the usability of Connect2Cap 2.0, offering triangulated insights that validate the observed outcomes and highlight the practicality and relevance of the tool in authentic teaching contexts.

3.1 The Impact on Activity Mastery among the Two Participants

The results in Figure 2 and 3 indicate that both students exhibited consistent and marked improvements in fine motor control and color matching over the intervention period.

Figure 2. This is a figure of Connect2Cap 2.0 mastery progress graph via matching method (student A)

Figure 3. This is a figure of Connect2Cap 2.0 mastery progress graph via matching method (student B)

3.2 Usability

Findings from teacher interviews highlighted four key themes: (i) improvement in fine motor skills through strengthening finger muscles as preparation for pre-writing activities; (ii) enhancement of students' focus during color-matching tasks; (iii) usability and accessibility, as the tool was easy to use and reduced reliance on teacher guidance; and (iv) practicality and sustainability, with the material being reusable, cost-effective, and suitable for long-term use.

4. DISCUSSION

These findings align with the broader literature demonstrating the effectiveness of structured, sensory-integrated interventions in improving motor and cognitive skills in children with ASD (Gaber et al., 2025). Moreover, physical activity interventions and targeted hand muscle exercises have been shown to produce lasting gains in motor function among children with ASD, further validating Connect2Cap's 2.0 focus on muscle-strengthening activities.

The broader applicability of Connect2Cap 2.0 is also a salient implication. Although developed for SEN students, its structured yet adaptable format suggests that it can be beneficial for typically developing preschoolers, particularly if modified to accommodate diverse ability levels and integrated with creative instructional strategies. Evidence from early childhood research supports the use of adaptive, hands-on media to foster fine motor and cognitive skills across a range of learner profiles (Marliyastuti et al., 2024).

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Connect2Cap 2.0 represents a promising, evidence-based tool for strengthening finger muscles and supporting color-cognitive tasks in both SEN and typically developing early learners. This innovation, grounded in interdisciplinary research and iterative educator feedback, highlights the value of integrating physical, cognitive, and creative dimensions into early intervention strategies for fine motor skill development. Further research with larger and more diverse samples is recommended to validate and refine its application across various educational contexts. Currently, this product is undergoing the process of registering intellectual property protection at Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM), emphasizing its contribution to strengthening the potential of SEN students through a positive and inclusive learning approach.

Acknowledgments: This study funded and supported by Makmal Pembelajaran Autisme, Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (TPU25)

References

- Fasikhah, S. S., & Yustika, S. (2025). Positive reinforcement to improve fine motor skills in children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). *KnE Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v10i7.18331>
- Gaber, S., Alzahrani, A. S., Dawsari, I. A., Hamad, A. M., & Alhajri, A. (2025). Developing gross and fine motor skills using sensory integration in children with moderate autism spectrum disorder. *European Journal of Educational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.14.1.297>
- Gonzalez, M. S., Ni, G., Lam, V., & Demopoulos, C. (2024). Beyond words: An investigation of fine motor skills and the verbal communication spectrum in autism. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2024.1379307>
- Huili, S., Cao, X., Guo, G., Yu, J., Yu, L., & Zhang, W. (2023). Research on the design of somatosensory interactive games for autistic children based on art therapy. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2023.1207023>
- Lin, L., Hwang, I., Hsu, C., Yu, W., Lai, P., Chen, Y., & Tu, Y. (2024). Comparing fine motor performance among young children with autism spectrum disorder, intellectual disability, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, and specific developmental disorder of motor function. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2024.1372980>
- Marliyastuti, N., Ardina, M., & Fitriana, S. (2024). Experimental Study: Coloring Activities with the Abur Wipe Technique as a Means of Early Childhood Fine Motor Development. *Journal of Early Childhood Development and Education*, 1(3), 93–99. <https://doi.org/10.58723/junior.v1i3.240>
- Mohandass, G., Muthusamy, R., & Ramachandran, S. (2023). Hand grip strengthening exercises on fine motor skills in children with autism spectrum disorder. *None*. <https://doi.org/10.56984/8zg07b63f>